

Innovation Analysis of ASEAN Countries

Louangrath, P.I. ★ and Fukbua, Thunchanok ★★

About the authors

★Louangrath, P.I. is an Assistant Professor in Business Administration at Bangkok University, Bangkok, Thailand. For correspondence, he could be reached by email at: Lecturepedia@gmail.com
★★Fukbua, Thunchanok is a research assistant.

ABSTRACT

The objective of this paper is to identify the determining factors for national innovation capabilities. The ASEAN 10 countries are used as proxy subjects for our studies. Secondary data from the World Economic Forum was used for testing. The WEF identified 12 categories of composite for national competitiveness index. We take these 12 composites and re-analyzed them for innovational capabilities. We identified innovation capabilities as dependent variable (Y), and the remaining 11 factors as independent variables (Xs): institutions, infrastructure, ICT adoption, macroeconomic stability, health, skills, product market, labor, financial system, market size, business dynamism. Correlation matrix was used to identify models. We found that product market, financial institution, business dynamics, and skills of the labor force are significant factors for innovation capabilities for the ASEAN countries. The R squared level for the proposed multiple regression was 0.9783 and the ANOVA F test value was 74.63 compared $F(8,8) = 3.44$ ($p = 0.0000$) with adjusted R squared at -0.95. This study also showed that the expected innovation capabilities of ASEAN countries are low; this finding implies that the ASEAN economies are still left in the Industry 3.0 despite their government mounded the policy of Industry 4.0. Economic growth in the ASEAN will continue to depend on manufacturing and export processing, not based on knowledge and innovation.

Keywords: ASEAN, Global Competitiveness Index, innovation

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1.0 INTRODUCTION

The objective of this paper is to analyze innovative capabilities of the 10 ASEAN countries. These ASEAN countries include: Brunei, Cambodia, Indonesia, Laos, Malaysia, Myanmar, Philippines, Singapore, Thailand, and Vietnam. We note that Myanmar lacks data. Thus, throughout the paper, ASEAN countries data will not contain Myanmar.

This paper is motivated by the inadequacy of innovation literature trying to make arguments about national innovation based on firm level strategies. Porter (1990), for instance, pretends to analysis competitiveness among nations, but failed to look at macro-economic factors in details. We look to multi-composite approach of the World Economic Forum (WEF) as the basis for macro-level analysis of innovation for nations.

Innovation research generally also focuses on intrinsic characteristics and factors within the organization. The purpose of this paper is to examine how external factors affect innovation at a national level. While the literature examines firm and industry innovation, we relied on the Global Competitive Index to study country level innovation.

This paper verified factors that significantly contribute to innovation at a national level. While firm innovation depends on factors that are intrinsic to the firm, national innovation depends on macro-economic factors. The WEF's 12 pillars for Global Competitiveness Index provide the basis for national innovation analysis. The WEF defines innovation capabilities composite to include: diversity of workforce, state of clusters development, international co-inventions, multi-stakeholder collaboration, scientific publications, and patent applications (WEF, p. 641).

Innovation contributes to national competitiveness. Innovation is a key element for national competitiveness. We examined the seminal argument made by Porter (1990) who recognized four contributing factors: factor conditions, demand condition, related and supporting industries and firm strategy (Porter, 1990; p. 78). Porter argued that these factors contribute to productivity and productivity contributes to national competitiveness. Porter explains: "The only meaningful concept of competitiveness at the national level is productivity. The principal goal of a nation is to produce a high and rising standard of living for its citizens. The ability to do so depends on the productivity with which a nation's labor and capital are employed." (Porter, p. 76).

The argument urged by Porter is problematic in that it tries to present a direct link between firms and the national economy. The empirical findings in this paper shows that *product market, financial institution, business dynamics, and skills level of the work force* are external to the firm. If competitiveness of a nation comes from innovation and national level innovation is determined by macro-economic factors, the argument of "firm strategy" by Porter may no longer hold sway in the current global economy. It would make more sense to present a more simplified argument that innovative firms depends on intrinsic factors at firm level, and likewise national innovation depends on macro-economic factors such as *product market, financial institution, business dynamics, and skills level of the work force*. This is the gap in the literature that this papers addresses.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

Innovation refers to improving products, services and existing processes (Leonard and Rayport, 1997). Damanpour (1991) shows three pairs of types of innovation: administrative innovation, technical innovation, process innovation. The technical innovations relate to basic activities of an organization and focus on product or process (Damanpour and Evan, 1984, Knight, 1967). The administrative innovations are indirectly related to basic activities of the organization and more directly to the anagement of those activities (Damanpour and Evan, 1984, Kimberly and Evanisko, 1981, Knight, 1967). Product innovations are represented by the new products or services introduced to meet the needs of the market (Knight, 1967, Utterback and Abernathy, 1975).

When authors speak of innovation, they refer to it as a process; however, innovation may occur as a component of the process that contribute to the result as a whole as an improved output (Henderson, Clark, 1990). Adoptive or creative innovation may be in this form Thompson (2004).

Some authors defined innovation in terms of effects, such as “revolutionary,” “disruptive,” “irregular” or “discovery” (Freeman 1974, Garcia and Calantone 2002, Tushman and Anderson 1986). Other authors (Damanpour, 1991; Dewar and Dutton, 1986) defined innovation in terms of incremental change in firm's competencies. Tushman and Anderson (1986) see innovation as intensified output for one firm while incapacitate competitors.

Innovation contributes positive outcome to the organization if it is adopted throughout the organization (Hansen and Birkinshaw, 2007). The literature identified innovation as a key to success in an organization (McAdam and Keogh, 2004; Edward *et al.*, 2005). Generally, innovation literature focuses on firm innovation in the context of administrative and technical innovation (Daft, (1978); Kimberly and Evanisko (1981). Innovation may be a form of change that comes as incremental or radical changes that completely changes the way the organization functions (Dewar and Dutton (1986).

Some literature claims that innovation is turning new ideas into practice (Handsen and Birkenshaw, 2007). Some identify employees as rich sources of innovation (Andriopoulos and Lowe, 2000). In order to rely on employees for contribution to novation, the organization must be opened to new ideas (Guimaraes and Langley, 1994; McAdam and McClelland, 2002). In such a case, innovation is a process ready to receive ideas from employees (Thamhain, 2003).

The most effective type of innovation is reinvention of existing knowledge, not just adopting innovation (Rogers, 1983). Adopting new innovation involves capital for technology transfer. Re-invention, on the other hand, requires the use of existing knowledge. Therefore, reinvention is more appropriate for capital poor organization (Seelos *et al.*, 2011).

There are different innovation levels among firms, industry and countries. This paper looked at the different level of innovation among the ASEAN countries and verified which among the twelve factors proffered by the WEF. While there are 12 factors that contribute to competitiveness, there are only four factors that contribute to innovation at a national level. These factors include: *product market, financial institution, business dynamics, and skills level of the work force.*

3.0 DATA AND METHODOLOGY

Secondary data was used for this paper. The annual report of the World Economic Forum (WEF) called the Global Competitiveness Index for 2017-2018 was used for this paper. The raw data of Global Competitiveness Index from the WEF is reproduced in Tables 1A and 1B. Our focus is on ASEAN countries. ASEAN has ten countries. In the WEF's report, Myanmar is left out because data was not available.

The WEF defined competitiveness of the economy according to the 12 pillars. These 12 pillars are: (1) institutions, (2) infrastructure, (3) ICT adoption, (4) macroeconomic stability, (5) health, (6) skills, (7) product market, (8) labor, (9) financial system, (10) market size, (11) business dynamism, and (12) innovation capabilities. In this paper, we are interested in innovation capabilities. We defined innovation capabilities as dependent variable (Y) and the remaining 11 pillars as possible independent variables (Xs.)

The score listed in Tables 1A and 1B are scores for competitiveness index produced by WEF. We used competitiveness score as the proxy for verifying the relationship between innovation capabilities and other 11 factors.

Table 1A: Global Competitiveness Index raw score

Country	Inst.	Infra.	ICT	Macro	Health	Skills
Brunei	58.30	71.30	76.20	73.70	85.90	66.00
Cambodia	41.90	51.70	44.40	74.40	62.90	41.00
Indonesia	57.90	66.80	61.10	89.70	71.70	64.10
Laos	44.50	57.50	42.70	68.50	59.60	49.50
Malaysia	68.70	77.90	69.10	100	82.60	74.20
Philippines	48.30	59.40	54.80	90.00	67.60	62.90

Singapore	80.70	95.70	85.20	92.60	100	76.00
Thailand	49.50	65.40	43.30	75.00	81.00	54.30
Vietnam	55.10	69.70	56.60	89.90	87.30	63.00

Table 1B: Global Competitiveness Index raw score

Country	Prod Mk	Labor	Finance	Mk size	Bus Dyn	Innovation
Brunei	60.90	64.20	51.20	37.00	58.50	33.90
Cambodia	50.00	59.70	53.60	46.20	45.30	31.20
Indonesia	58.50	57.80	63.90	81.60	69.00	37.10
Laos	53.50	55.40	84.10	73.00	73.80	55.50
Malaysia	63.60	70.20	51.30	41.10	40.10	27.40
Philippines	56.90	64.50	67.90	70.20	65.80	37.20
Singapore	81.20	80.20	89.30	71.10	74.70	75.00
Thailand	52.10	55.60	62.30	70.90	53.70	33.40
Vietnam	53.40	63.30	84.20	74.90	71.00	42.10

The 11 pillars that we used as independent variables are factors external to the firm. In the literature, writers generally focus on factors that are internal to the firm when studying innovation. In this paper, we looked at innovation at a national level; thus, the independent variables are external to the firm. The WEF’s composite for innovation capabilities include: diversity of workforce, state of clusters development, international co-inventions, multi-stakeholder collaboration, scientific publications, and patent applications (WEF, p. 641).

Model identification was accomplished by inter-variables pairing and then calculate the value for Pearson correlation coefficient:

$$r = b \left(\frac{S_x}{S_y} \right) \tag{1}$$

where b = slope of the regression line between x and y (Appendix 1); S_x = standard deviation of x and S_y = standard deviation of y . The significance test for the correlation is determined by the T test:

$$T = \frac{r\sqrt{n-2}}{\sqrt{(1-r^2)}} \tag{2}$$

Once significant pairs are identified (Appendix 3), we construct the first level of analysis by simple regression among two variables. With know significant regressors, we then combine multiple variables to construct multiple regression models. The multiple regression models were tested for significance by ANOVA, thus:

$$F = \frac{MSR}{MSE} \tag{3}$$

where $MSE = SSE / n - p - 1$; $SSE = \sum (y_i - \hat{y})^2$; $MSR = SSR / p$; and $SSR = (\hat{y} - \bar{y})^2$. The coefficient of determination for multiple regression is:

$$R^2 = \frac{SSR}{SST} = \frac{SSR}{SSE + SSR} \tag{4}$$

The adjusted R squared is given by:

$$R^2_{adj} = 1 - \left(\frac{(1 - R^2)(N - 1)}{N - p - 1} \right) \tag{5}$$

where N = number of observations and p = number of variables used in the model (parameters).

4.0 FINDINGS AND ANALYSIS

As part of model identification, we implemented inter-variable correlation analysis (Appendix 1) then verify the intensity of the relationship among variables with the T test. The result of the T test is presented in Table 2. The threshold for significance level was fixed under ideal condition, $T(\infty, 0.95) = 1.64$. Under this protocol, four factors were identified: *infrastructure*, *product market*, *financial system*, and *business dynamics*. These significant relationships are based on single factor analysis, i.e. one Y to one X. The correlation matrix is presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Correlation coefficient matrix for model identification

X*	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
1		0.74	0.76	0.73	0.23	0.90	0.79	0.76	0.47	0.54	0.87	0.98
2	-		0.46	0.85	-0.20	0.31	0.77	0.72	0.77	0.78	0.58	0.90
3	-	-		0.85	0.07	-0.02	0.13	0.74	0.52	0.87	0.90	0.67
4	-	-	-		0.50	0.27	-0.02	0.22	0.65	0.88	0.87	0.84
5	-	-	-	-		0.66	0.16	-0.07	0.08	0.85	0.92	0.90
6	-	-	-	-	-		0.26	0.12	0.10	0.05	0.85	0.93
7	-	-	-	-	-	-		0.36	-0.04	-0.26	0.31	0.87
8	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		0.04	0.14	0.00	0.21
9	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		0.37	0.21	-0.06
10	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		0.55	0.13
11	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		0.47
12	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	

*(1) institutions, (2) infrastructure, (3) ICT adoption, (4) macroeconomic stability, (5) health, (6) skills, (7) product market, (8) labor, (9) financial system, (10) market size, (11) business dynamism, and (12) innovation

The model identification under correlation matrix is later confirmed with simple regression protocol presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Significance test of (x,y) pairs

X*	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
1		-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
2	2.83		-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
3	5.57	4.64		-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
4	2.41	1.90	1.71		-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
5	4.09	5.62	3.30	1.42		-	-	-	-	-	-	-
6	5.36	4.57	4.67	3.22	3.13		-	-	-	-	-	-
7	6.80	6.26	5.01	1.62	2.75	3.45		-	-	-	-	-
8	4.70	4.31	4.24	2.27	2.87	3.18	5.50		-	-	-	-

9	0.57	0.87	0.13	0.20	0.59	0.35	0.88	0.64		-	-	-
10	-0.16	0.01	-0.70	0.26	-0.18	-0.06	-0.04	-0.54	2.82		-	-
11	0.34	0.56	0.37	-0.09	0.32	0.44	0.73	0.19	4.26	3.06		-
12	1.41	1.74	1.04	0.10	1.02	0.73	2.32	1.52	4.32	1.39	2.94	

In simple regression modeling, we see the level of contribution of each significant factor to innovation at the national level. Two indicators are worthy of mentioning, namely the *intercept* and *slope* of the linear regression. For infrastructure, the identified model is infrastructure significantly contributes to national innovation: $Y = -2.02 + 0.64x$. We note that without infrastructure, national innovation is negative; however, with the presence of infrastructure, the rate of change of innovation is 0.64 times. The WEF defined the infrastructure as transport and utility which include: Quality of road network, quality of road infrastructure, railroad density, efficiency of train services, airport connectivity, efficiency of air transport services, liner shipping connectivity, efficiency of seaport services, electricity access, electricity quality, exposure to unsafe drinking water, and reliability of water supply (WEF, p.634-35).

The second model we identified is the labor market significantly contributes to national innovation: $Y = -16.05 + 0.85x$. Without the labor market, national innovation dips down to -16.05 points. The WEF defined the labor market as: Redundancy costs, hiring and firing practices, cooperation in labor-employer relations, flexibility of wage determination, active labor policies, workers' rights, ease of hiring foreign labor, internal labor mobility, reliance on professional management, pay and productivity, and female participation in labor force (WEF, pp. 638-39).

The third model we identified is market size significantly contributes to national innovation: $Y = -12.36 + 0.88x$. Without market size, national innovation dips to -12.36; however, with adequate market size, innovation changes at a rate of 0.88 time any given unit of innovation a country achieved. The WEF defined the market size as gross domestic product and imports of goods and services (WEF, p. 639).

The fourth model we identified is business dynamics significantly contributes to national innovation: $Y = -12.36 + 0.88x$. With business dynamics, national innovation is hindered by -12.36 points. With business dynamics in the economy, innovation increases at a rate of 0.88 units. The WEF defined the business dynamics as cost of starting a business, time to start a business, insolvency recovery rate, insolvency regulatory framework, attitudes toward entrepreneurial risk, willingness to delegate authority, growth of innovative companies, and companies embracing disruptive ideas (WEF, p. 640).

Table 4. Simple regression of determinant factors for innovation, $n = 9$ countries.

Influencing factor	Simple linear regression equation	Significance T Value	One-sided p Value	R squared Value
Institution	$Y = 9.43 + 0.57x$	1.41	0.1007	0.22
Infrastructure	$Y = -2.02 + 0.64x$	1.74	0.0626	0.30
ICT adoption	$Y = 20.08 + 0.36x$	1.04	0.1668	0.13
Macro	$Y = 37.19 + 0.52x$	0.09	0.4625	0.001
Health	$Y = 9.64 + 0.41x$	1.02	0.1710	0.13
Skills	$Y = 19.94 + 0.35X$	0.73	0.2454	0.22
Product market	$Y = -20.07 + 1.04x$	2.32	0.0266	0.25
Labor market	$Y = -18.18 + 0.94x$	1.52	0.0865	0.73
Financial inst.	$Y = -16.05 + 0.85x$	4.32	0.0017	0.33
Market size	$Y = 15.15 + 0.43x$	1.38	0.1040	0.55
Bus. dynamics	$Y = -12.36 + 0.88x$	2.94	0.0109	0.07

From the combined coefficient of the intercepts of simple regression, we could determine the base-level of innovative capabilities. Using Weibull QQ plot to obtain the predictive function to

forecast the base level of innovation capabilities of ASEAN countries, the linear predictive line is $Y = 0.98 + 2.98x$. By converting the intercept from its logged form, and substituting the observed score, the predictive value for the base innovative capabilities is 14.25 on a scale of 100.

Using the same method to obtain the predictive function for the slopes of the series, we obtained the Weibull QQ plot equation: $Y = 1.31 + 1.72x$. The predictive value for the rate of change of innovative capabilities is -0.22 which indicates a deteriorating trend ($1/\beta = 1/-0.22 = -4.55$).

Table 5. Multiple regression of determinant factors for innovation

Factor	Coefficient	T value	One side pValue
Intercept	-43.61	7.79	0.0007
Product market (x1)	1.37	9.37	0.0004
Financial inst. (x2)	0.51	4.91	0.0040
Business dynamics (x3)	0.19	1.65	0.0873
Skills (x4)	-0.68	5.74	0.0022
Test Results	Observed values	Reference values	
<i>ANOVA F test</i>	74.63	F(8,8)* = 3.18	
<i>R squared</i>	0.98	$-1 < R^2 < 1$	
<i>Adjusted R squared</i>	0.95	$-1 < R^2 < 1$	

* $n = 9$ and $p = 4$.

The predictive model from multiple regression is $Y = -43.61 + 1.37x_1 + 0.51x_2 + 0.19x_3 - 0.68x_4$ with the adjusted R squared of 0.9783. The significance test was accomplished ANOVA. The result F test was 74.63 compared $F(8,8) = 3.44$. We note that the ASEAN is not known for innovation. The intercept of the proposed model is negative. It means that without supporting factors, such as product market (x1), financial institution (x2), business dynamics (x3), and skills (x4), there is no innovation among the ASEAN countries. We note also that the sign of the coefficient for skill level of the work force is negative which implies that the labor market in the ASEAN economies is low.

The WEF's skills composite include: (i) mean years of schooling; (iii) extent of staff training; (iv) quality of vocational training; (v) skill set of graduates; (vi) digital skills among active population; (vii) ease of finding skilled employees; (viii) school life expectancy; (ix) critical thinking in teaching; and (x) pupil-to-teacher ratio in primary education (WEF, pp. 637-38). The coefficient for skill composite in the proposed model is -0.68. This negative coefficient raises speculation of interactive effect between skills composite with other factors in the model. Skills by itself were not significant ($p = 0.22$) in the simple regression model and in the correlation matrix, it had a low T score of 0.73. Thus, we examine the interaction effect between skills and other factors. The test for interaction effect is given by:

$$T_{b_m b_n} = \frac{b_m - b_n}{\sqrt{\frac{n_m SE_m^2 + n_n SE_n^2}{n_m - n_n - 2}}} \quad (6)$$

We found that there is significant interaction between product market (x1: $T = 3.59$) and skills set, and between business dynamics (x3: $T = 1.64$) and skills set.

The interaction effect between variables is measured by $b_k = \hat{b} + b_m - b_n - b_0$ where $\hat{b} = \bar{y} - (b_n + b_0) - b_m$. We found that the interaction between product market and skills of the labor force (x1x4) is 127.26; the interaction between financial institutions and skills of the labor force

(x3x4) is 129.62. Thus, we have two additional modified proposed models after accommodating for the interaction: $Y_{(1,4)} = -43.61 + 1.37x_1 + 0.51x_2 + 0.19x_3 - 0.68x_4 + 127.26x_1x_4$ and the interaction for the second pair is $Y_{(3,4)} = -43.61 + 1.37x_1 + 0.51x_2 + 0.19x_3 - 0.68x_4 + 129.62x_3x_4$.

5.0 CONCLUSION

In this paper, we examined the secondary data from the WEF's Global Competitiveness Index report and re-analyzed ASEAN in the context of innovation capabilities. We learned two things from this study. Firstly, among the factors making countries competitive, there are four factors that are relevant to the country's innovation capabilities; these factors are: product market (x1), financial institution (x2), business dynamics (x3), and skill level of the labor force (x4). Secondly, without the four supporting factors, ASEAN economies are not innovative. This lack of innovation implies that the ASEAN economies are still in the Industry 3.0 era, not catching up with the current policy trend of "Industry 4.0" if the new economy is knowledge-based and being innovative. We use these findings to point out the fact. We do not pretend to offer any policy recommendation for change or improve the current condition. The lack of innovative capabilities of the ASEAN economies is an intrinsic characteristic; to enumerate list of recommendations is pretentious.

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Appendix 1 Construction of simple regression model

$$\left. \begin{aligned} I &= n \sum XY - \sum X \sum Y \\ II &= n \sum X^2 - (\sum X)^2 \\ b &= \frac{I}{II} \\ a &= \bar{Y} - b\bar{X} \end{aligned} \right\} Y = a + bX$$

where a = intercept where the regression line $Y = a + bX$ crosses the Y-intercept when $X = 0$; b = slope or the rate of change in Y with respect to the change in X.

Fig. 1a.

Appendix 2
 ANOVA Test for multiple regression model

Proposed model from empirical data:

$$Y = -43.61 + 1.37x_1 + 0.51x_2 + 0.19x_3 - 0.68x_4$$

Interaction effect modified models:

$$Y_{(1,4)} = -43.61 + 1.37x_1 + 0.51x_2 + 0.19x_3 - 0.68x_4 + 127.26x_1x_4$$

$$Y_{(3,4)} = -43.61 + 1.37x_1 + 0.51x_2 + 0.19x_3 - 0.68x_4 + 129.62x_3x_4$$

Table 1A. ANOVA data

Country	Product Market	Financial Institution	Business Dynamics	Skills Labor	Innovation Capabilities
Brunei	60.90	51.20	58.50	66.00	33.90
Cambodia	50.00	53.60	45.30	41.00	31.20
Indonesia	58.50	63.90	69.00	64.10	37.10
Laos	53.50	84.10	73.80	49.50	55.50
Malaysia	63.60	51.30	40.10	74.20	27.40
Philippines	56.90	67.90	65.80	62.90	37.20
Singapore	81.20	89.30	74.70	76.00	75.00
Viet Nam	52.10	62.30	53.70	54.30	33.40
Thailand	53.40	84.20	71.00	63.00	42.10

Table 2a. ANOVA calculations

Country	y	\bar{y}	\hat{y}	$(y - \hat{y})^2$	$(\hat{y} - \bar{y})^2$
Brunei	33.90	41.42	33.49	0.17	62.92
Cambodia	31.20	41.42	33.77	6.62	58.51
Indonesia	37.10	41.42	39.93	8.00	2.23
Laos	55.50	41.42	53.93	2.47	156.39
Malaysia	27.40	41.42	28.33	0.87	171.35
Philippines	37.20	41.42	39.96	7.62	2.14
Singapore	75.00	41.42	77.21	4.88	1,280.77
Viet Nam	33.40	41.42	33.91	0.26	56.51
Thailand	42.10	41.42	44.40	5.29	8.87
<i>SSE</i>				36.17	
<i>SSR</i>				1,799.69	
<i>MSE = SSE / n - p - 1</i>				6.03	
<i>MSR = SSR / p</i>				449.92	
<i>F = MSR / MSE</i>				74.63	
<i>F(8,8)</i>				3.18	
<i>R squared</i>				0.98	
<i>Adj. R squared</i>				0.95	

Appendix 3 Model identification

Table 3a. Raw score for ASEAN Global Competitive Index (mean score); WEF 2017-18

Competitive Score	Inst	Infra	ICT	Macro	Health	Skills	Prod	Labor	Finan	Market	Bus Dyn	Innov
Brunei	58.30	71.30	76.20	73.70	85.90	66.00	60.90	64.20	51.20	37.00	58.50	33.90
Cambodia	41.90	51.70	44.40	74.40	62.90	41.00	50.00	59.70	53.60	46.20	45.30	31.20
Indonesia	57.90	66.80	61.10	89.70	71.70	64.10	58.50	57.80	63.90	81.60	69.00	37.10
Lao PDR	44.50	57.50	42.70	68.50	59.60	49.50	53.50	55.40	84.10	73.00	73.80	55.50
Malaysia	68.70	77.90	69.10	100.00	82.60	74.20	63.60	70.20	51.30	41.10	40.10	27.40
Philippines	48.30	59.40	54.80	90.00	67.60	62.90	56.90	64.50	67.90	70.20	65.80	37.20
Singapore	80.70	95.70	85.20	92.60	100.00	76.00	81.20	80.20	89.30	71.10	74.70	75.00
Viet Nam	49.50	65.40	43.30	75.00	81.00	54.30	52.10	55.60	62.30	70.90	53.70	33.40
Thailand	55.10	69.70	56.60	89.90	87.30	63.00	53.40	63.30	84.20	74.90	71.00	42.10

Table 4a. Linear relationship among variables in XY pairs

SLOPE	Inst	Infra	ICT	Macro	Health	Skills	Prod	Labor	Finan	Market	Bus Dyn	Innov
Institution	-											
Infra.	0.93	-										
ICT	0.73	0.74	-									
Macro	0.76	0.69	0.75	-								
Health	0.79	0.89	0.90	0.39	-							
Skills	0.98	1.26	1.17	0.75	0.89	-						
Product	1.22	1.26	1.42	0.60	1.00	0.95	-					
Labor	1.36	1.39	1.63	0.90	1.22	1.10	1.08	-				
Financial	0.17	0.27	0.05	0.06	0.19	0.10	0.20	0.12	-			
Market	-	0.04	0.00	-	0.23	0.06	-	0.05	-	0.10	0.66	-
Bus. dyn.	0.12	0.21	0.17	-	0.03	0.12	0.15	0.20	0.05	1.00	0.99	-
Innovation	0.39	0.48	0.37	0.03	0.32	0.20	0.42	0.26	0.26	0.52	0.63	-

SD	Inst	Infra	ICT	Macro	Health	Skills	Prod	Labor	Finan	Market	Bus Dyn	Innov
Institution	-											
Infra.	13.78	-										
ICT	13.49	14.44	-									
Macro	18.16	14.44	17.97	-								
Health	16.58	13.50	16.68	12.12	-							
Skills	11.76	12.33	13.00	15.82	14.56	-						
Product	10.74	12.01	12.25	16.17	14.68	10.16	-					
Labor	10.73	10.70	11.92	13.96	12.79	9.52	8.76	-				
Fin inst	14.54	13.57	15.22	15.20	14.60	13.67	13.36	11.80	-			
Market	14.60	14.71	15.53	17.35	16.37	11.29	12.12	11.49	15.52	-		
Bus. dyn.	12.41	12.93	13.58	16.26	15.05	11.63	12.00	10.56	13.82	14.34	-	
Innovation	15.28	19.39	17.24	25.21	23.08	16.39	17.67	16.89	19.77	18.89	16.89	-

Table 5a. Correlation coefficient among XY pairs

CORRELATION	Inst	Infra	ICT	Macro	Health	Skills	Prod	Labor	Finan	Market	Bus Dyn	Innov
Institution	-											
Infra.	0.98	-										
ICT	0.90	0.87	-									
Macro	0.67	0.58	0.54	-								
Health	0.84	0.90	0.78	0.47	-							
Skills	0.90	0.87	0.87	0.77	0.76	-						
Product	0.93	0.92	0.88	0.52	0.72	0.79	-					
Labor	0.87	0.85	0.85	0.65	0.74	0.77	0.90	-				
Financial	0.21	0.31	0.05	0.08	0.22	0.13	0.31	0.23	-			
Market	-	0.06	0.00	-	0.26	0.10	-	0.02	-	0.73	-	
Bus. dyn.	0.13	0.21	0.14	-	0.04	0.12	0.16	0.27	0.07	0.85	0.76	-
Innovation	0.47	0.55	0.37	0.04	0.36	0.26	0.66	0.50	0.85	0.46	0.74	-